

Residues of organophosphate pesticides in vegetables in traditional market and supermarket of Bogor city, West Java

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ABSTRACT

Vegetables are a commodity that is needed as a source of nutrition for humans. Vegetables are broadly a source of fiber, vitamins and minerals that are good enough for the body and efficacious to improve health and metabolism. The vegetable plants are very susceptible to pests and diseases, farmers to control pests and diseases use pesticides. Organophosphate class pesticides are increasingly used for vegetable crops because of their beneficial properties for farmers. Organophosphate pesticides are selective, not persistent in the soil, and does not cause resistance to insects, works as contact poisons, stomach poisons and also respiratory poisons. Improper use of pesticides can lead to pesticide residues, as a result vegetables are often contaminated by pesticide residues. Pesticide residues contained in vegetables can have a direct or indirect impact on consumers. Organophosphate pesticides by inhibiting the activity of cholinesterase enzymes, so that acetylcholine is not hydrolyzed. The possible effects on humans are bloody or runny nose, coughing, chest pain, shortness of breath and difficulty or wheezing due to narrowing or excess fluid in the bronchial tube. This study aims to determine the content of pesticide residues in various types of vegetables in the city of Bogor, West Java. The research method was carried out by taking cabbage, potato and carrot vegetables in several vegetable sellers in traditional and supermarket markets in the city of Bogor, West Java. Vegetable samples as much as ± 10 g were extracted using the QuEChERS method. The results of extracts were identified as organophosphate residues using Gas Chromatography (GC). The results of the study showed that some vegetable sample (cabbage, potato, and carrots) contained pesticide residues, i.e. chlorpyrifos, profenofos and diazinon. Chlorpyrifos pesticide residue concentrations of 0.0041-0.0295 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, profenofos 0.0018-0.0222 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ and diazinon 0.0033-0.0144 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. This value is still below the pesticide BMR threshold value based on SNI 7313 in 2008.

Keywords: *Residues, Pesticides, Vegetables, Traditional Markets, Supermarkets, Bogor*

INTRODUCTION

Organophosphate (OP) insecticides are often also referred to as phosphorus insecticide, phosphates, phosphorous esters, or phosphoric acid

esters. Broadly speaking, compounds in this class are derivatives of phosphoric acid, consists of aliphatic, phenyl and heterocyclic derivatives (Sogorb and Vanova, 2002). Most organophosphate compounds are esters or thiol derivatives of phosphate, phosphonate or amorphous phosphoric acid (Sogorb and Vanova, 2002). The use of organophosphate insecticides has been started since 1930 and has increased so rapidly since the prohibition of organochlorine insecticides in the 1970s.

The use of intensive organophosphate pesticides in agriculture has left pesticide residues in plants and has become a problem for both the environment and humans. Syahbirin (2001) explains that there are three types of organophosphates that are often used in vegetables and fruits, namely diazinon, dimetoate and chlorpyrifos. Insecticide residues found in agricultural products, such as vegetables, can be caused by direct exposure to insecticides sprayed when controlling plant-destroying pests, in addition to the absorption of insecticides in the soil by the roots of plants. Broccoli vegetables grown in Cihanjuang Rahayu Village, Parongpong Subdistrict, West Bandung Regency have organophosphate insecticidal content that exceeds the Maximum Residue Limit (LMR) of 10-82% based on SNI 7313: 2008 (Amilia et al., 2016). Sungkawa (2008) reported that organophosphate insecticides are one of the most common types of insecticides used by shallot farmers in Brebes Regency with an application frequency of 5-30 times per planting season (\pm 60 days). The use of chronic toxic insecticides such as organophosphates is predicted to cause changes in the balance of biological populations which results in a decline in biodiversity of various ecosystems. The results of pesticide residue analysis on cabbage showed that the dominant active ingredient of endosulfan was found in cabbage samples from both Malang and Cianjur, with the highest pesticide residue of 7.4 ppb analyzed from samples taken from farmers in Cianjur. Other residues include pesticides containing active ingredients chlorpyrifos, meditation, malathion, and carbaryl (Munarso et al., 2009)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was carried out in the laboratory of Agrochemical Material Residues, Indonesia Agricultural Environmental Research Institute, Laladon Bogor. Implementation time starts from April 2017 to July 2017. Research materials include samples of soil taken in cabbage, potato and carrot vegetables in traditional markets and supermarkets in the city of Bogor, West Java. Chemicals for the analysis of chlorpyrifos insecticide residues consist of: acetonitrile, $MgSO_4$, Na Ac, anhydrous sodium sulfate, potassium hydroxide, cellite 545, chlorpyrifos insecticide 99.5% standard, 99.4% Propenofos and 99.5% Diazinon.

The tools used for soil sampling consist of, for example, 450 GC Variant gas chromatography which is equipped with a thermionic specific detector (TSD) detector, shaker, centrifuge, rotating vacuum evaporator (evaporator-Buchi R-114).

Validation of Chlorpyrifos, Profenofos and Diazinon Insecticidal Analysis and Identification Methods

Validation of an analysis method is an important factor in an analysis measurement. Analytical methods that have been proven validity of measurement results, can be accounted for and used as a basis for the next calculation. Some parameters in conducting validation include linearity, selectivity, accuracy, accuracy, limit of detection and limit of quantification. The linearity parameter describes the linear relationship between concentration and absorption so that the equations obtained can be used to calculate the concentration of active substances in the sample. The selectivity parameter describes the ability of the analysis method to separate active substances from other components. The accuracy of the analysis illustrates the closeness of the test results in several repetitions, the accuracy describes the proximity of the test results with the actual value. Limit of detection describes the minimum amount that can be detected by the analysis method, and limit of quantification describes the minimum amount that can be detected by quantitative methods that can be accounted for quantitatively (Snyder et al., 1997; Miller and Crowther, 2000).

Extraction and Identification Procedure

The streamlined procedure given below was used for extraction and cleanup in the final method. Any alterations made in the method in experiments will be mentioned when discussing the results. Weigh 10.00 ± 0.05 g of thoroughly comminuted sample into a 10 mL acetonitrile, shake 30 s, Add 6 g anhydrous $MgSO_4$ and 1.5 g anhydrous Na Ac (do not get the powders in the threads or rims of the tubes). Seal the tubes and shake vigorously for 1 min by hand (3-5 tubes can be held per hand) ensuring that the solvent interacts well with the entire sample and that crystalline agglomerates are broken up sufficiently. Centrifuge the tubes at 3450 rcf (5000 rpm on the centrifuge we used) for 1 min. Transfer the extracts (upper layer) to dispersive-SPE tubes containing 50 mg PSA + 150 mg anhydrous $MgSO_4$ /mL of extract. Cap the tubes well and mix the extract with the sorbent/dessicant for 20 s. Centrifuge the tubes at 5000 rpm. Identification to GC, The GC separation was conducted on a Restek Rtx-1705 ms capillary column (30 m, 0.25 mm id, 0.25 μ m film thickness) with the following conditions: N_2 constant flow, 28 mL/min; inlet temperature, 250°C;

injection volume, 2 µL (splitless); detector temperature, 300°C; initial oven temperature, 150 °C, held for 1.5 min, then a 20 °C/min ramp to 200 °C followed by a 25 °C/min ramp to 250 °C (held for 16 min) (Lehotay et al., 2005).

$$\text{Residue Concentration : } R = \frac{Ac}{As} \times Cs \times \frac{Df}{Sw}$$

Keterangan :

- R = Residue (µg/g)
- Ac= Area sample (µV.min)
- As= Area Standart (µV.min)
- Cs= Consentration Standart (mg/g)
- Sv= Sample weight (mL)
- Df= Dilution factor (mL)

Validation of chlorpyrifos, Profenofos and Diazinon residual analysis methods.

In the preliminary test the measurement of the detection and recovery limit was carried out by measuring the residual content of chlorpyrifos, profenofos and diazinon insecticides. Cabbage vegetables, potatoes and carrots that have been mashed by blending, then added the active ingredients of chlorpyrifos, profenofos and diazinon insecticides until the concentration of each is 0.2 mg/kg and repeated seven times. The calculation results obtained the detection limit of chlorpyrifos of 0.0021 mg/kg, profenofos 0.0025 mg/kg and diazinon 0.0017 mg/kg, with these results the method used for the analysis of chlorpyrifos and diazinone insecticides in cabbage vegetables, potatoes and carrots has a capacity of 0.0021 mg/kg for chlorpyrifos, 0.0025 mg/kg for profenofos and diazinone 0.0017 mg/kg (Table 1).

Table 1. Validation of methods for analyzing insecticide residues in vegetable samples

Insecticides	Parameter	
	Detection limit (mg/kg)	Recovery (%)
Chlorpyrifos	0.0021	91.20
Profenofos	0.0025	95.50
Diazinon	0.0017	94.82

Testing the recovery value (recovery test) is done by adding the chlorophyllos, profenofos and diazinon insecticidal active ingredients to the vegetable medium which has been mashed by using a belender, and the vegetables are also analyzed without enriching it with insecticidal active ingredients. The average data from the results of the recovery test for

chlorpyrifos insecticides were 91.2%, profenofos 95.50 and diazinon were 94.82 mg/kg (Table 1). Based on data recovery it can be said that the method to be used for the analysis of chlorpyrifos insecticide residues in vegetable samples is sufficient to meet the requirements. There coffery value of a method to be used must be at 80-110% (AOAC, 2002).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The content of chlorpyrifos pesticides, profenofos and diazinon from cabbage, potatoes and carrots taken from traditional markets is not significantly different, this can be caused by vegetables sent to traditional markets and supermarkets from the same source. Potatoes and carrots contain smaller pesticide residues compared to cabbage vegetables, this can be caused by

Table 2. The results of insecticide residue analysis on vegetable samples

Types of vegetables	Location	Residue (mg/kg)		
		Chlorpyrifos	Profenofos	Diazinon
Cabbage	Traditional market A	0.0402 ± 0.002	0.0087 ± 0.002	0.0144 ± 0.003
	Traditional market B	0.0176 ± 0.005	0.0096 ± 0.002	0.0135 ± 0.005
	Traditional market C	0.0295 ± 0.007	0.0171 ± 0.005	0.0141 ± 0.004
	Supermarket A	0.0133 ± 0.004	0.0064 ± 0.004	0.0057 ± 0.003
	Supermarket B	0.0152 ± 0.003	0.0073 ± 0.001	0.0072 ± 0.002
Potato	Traditional market A	0.0077 ± 0.001	0.0018 ± 0.001	0.0045 ± 0.001
	Traditional market B	0.0042 ± 0.001	0.0032 ± 0.001	0.0069 ± 0.001
	Traditional market C	0.0041 ± 0.001	0.0031 ± 0.001	0.0048 ± 0.001
	Supermarket A	0.0041 ± 0.001	0.0035 ± 0.001	0.0047 ± 0.001
	Supermarket B	0.0052 ± 0.001	0.0019 ± 0.001	0.0033 ± 0.001
Carrot	Traditional market A	0.0178 ± 0.004	0.0112 ± 0.009	0.0033 ± 0.001
	Traditional market B	0.0169 ± 0.002	0.0283 ± 0.006	0.0049 ± 0.001
	Traditional market C	0.0192 ± 0.002	0.0222 ± 0.002	0.0055 ± 0.001
	Supermarket A	0.0133 ± 0.003	0.0117 ± 0.001	0.0055 ± 0.003
	Supermarket B	0.0078 ± 0.001	0.0196 ± 0.001	0.0036 ± 0.001

Pesticides applied to control plant pests will be directly exposed to cabbage leaves, while in potato tubers and mortles, pesticides will first fall to the soil and then absorb into the tissues root.

Table. 3. Maximum residual limitin vegetable

Types of vegetables	Chlorpyrifos (mg/kg)	Profenofos (mg/kg)	Diazinon (mg/kg)
Cabbage	0.05	1	0.5
Potato	0.01	2	0.01
Carrot	0.5	0.1	0.5

Reference :the maximum residue based on SNI 7313 2008

The residual content of chlorpyrifos pesticides, profenofos and diazinon tang originating from traditional markets is still below the threshold determined by the Indonesian National Standard (SNI) no. 7313 of 2008. The maximum limits for chlorpyrifos, profenofos and diazinon pesticide residues in cabbage were 0.05, 1 and 0.5 mg/kg, respectively, for potatoes at 0.01, 2 and 0.01 mg/kg, while for carrots at 0.5, 0.1 and 0.5 mg/kg (Table 3).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Vegetables cabbage, potatoes and carrots taken in traditional markets and supermarkets contain chlorpyrifos, profenofos and diazinon insecticides.
2. The highest pesticide residue content was obtained from cabbage vegetables, namely chlorpyrifos at $0.0133 \pm 0.004 - 0.0402 \pm 0.002$ mg/kg, profenofos $0.0064 \pm 0.004 - 0.0087 \pm 0.002$ mg/kg and diazinon $0.0073 \pm 0.001 - 0.0144 \pm 0.003$ mg/kg
3. The residual content of cabbage, potatoes and carrots is still below the maximum residue based on SNI 7313 2008

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